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***Fishery Earth Observation,
Modeling and Prediction (FJOMP)***

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Final Report

by

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1 Introduction

About 30 years after the start of the satellite Earth Observation (EO) era, we are facing a situation with increased and improved availability of satellite Earth observation data. Some of the early EO sensors are still maintained with compatible sensor systems and the tendency among the world-wide Space Agencies is that it is essential to obtain and maintain comparable EO time series over periods of decades. Mapping of marine environmental phenomenon such as: sea surface temperature (SST), ocean topography, sea ice concentration and extent, ocean colour, etc. will be provided by at least two to three different satellite systems over at least the next five years period. Individually each of these satellite sensors will provide important information for both research and operational monitoring. However, regular, consistent synergetic and integrated use of these data with other observations and numerical prediction model tools are needed to fully exploit the available information about our environment.

The longer the time series of consistent EO data are, the more suitable they become for trend and other statistical analysis in conjunction with other information sources such as fish stock assessments. The longest consistent EO time series over oceans are about 20 years (passive microwave mapping of sea ice, and infrared sensing of SST by AVHRR). In addition time series of ocean topography (currents) have been regularly obtained from satellite altimetry during the last 10-15 years. Regular long time series of ocean colour data, on the other hand, is lacking with a large gap of more than 12 years between the CZCS and the SeaWiFS sensors.

Long time series of (30-50 years) of information from the fisheries research and management are available for major parts of the Norwegian marine and coastal areas. The use of this information in conjunction with the EO data will enable us to search for relations between the inter-annual variation in the marine physical environment and the fish stock assessment, catch statistics and other information currently used within the fisheries management (see Pettersson et al, 2000).

The scope of this report is to identify the most relevant and appropriate physical marine data and their existing data products also making use of satellite Earth observation data of relevance to fisheries research and management. A systematic analyse of environmental and global change data have been performed in combination with the regularly used fisheries and other biological information used by the Norwegian fisheries research and management. The geographical regions analysed are in constituency with the ICES fishery statistics areas (Figure 1). The most profound correlations have been identified and used for prognostic estimates of future one to three years predictions fisheries parameters.

2 The FJOMP database

The Fishery, Earth Observation, Modelling and Prediction (FJOMP) data base consists of a collection of fisheries information time series, time series from field data covering physical marine environmental information, international databases (e.g. NCEP), satellite data, simulations results from numerical hydro dynamical models, and other relevant time series (e.g. polar front extension index). The FJOMP database is built on a hierarchy of catalogues and files. These files are in NetCDF format, and have a unique name within the database. The file hierarchic is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1. Overview of the major current systems in the Nordic Seas and the Barents Sea, together with the ICES fishery statistics areas for the same region.

For convenience the date for each dataset are set to the 1st day of the period in question (i.e. the 1st January for yearly data, 1st of month for monthly data etc.). Tools for extracting data from the database has been implemented by use of MATLAB.

The different dataset /sources are briefly described below and for a more thorough description it is referred to the FJOMP Users Manual (Handegard and Furevik, 2003). The FJOMP database is dynamical in the sense that it is easy to add new time series, or to update and extend existing datasets in the database. This facilitates a continued post project use and development of the database and its applications.

Figure 2 The structure of the FJOMP database.

3 The environmental and satellite data

During the FJOMP project implementation 4.94 GB of data have been gathered for a total of more than 70 fish and climate/environment parameters. Some of the parameters discussed further in the analysis are described in the following.

3.1 Fisheries data

The data are statistically yearly time series collected from different sources, mostly ICES and IMR. Most of the fisheries data are on North East Arctic Cod, Norwegian spring spawning herring and Barents Sea Caplin. On the other species mostly catch is stored. The data sets are mainly one-dimensional (time). Exceptions are VPA (Virtual Population Analysis) data at age, which is two-dimensional (age group and time).

3.2 Environmental data

The data is a collection of one-dimensional yearly time series from field, models and calculated indices. The average temperature data are based on Russian and IMR field data from standard sections (e.g. the Kola section). The data sets are one-dimensional (time).

3.3 Environmental monthly

The data is a collection of one-dimensionally monthly time series from field, models and calculated indices. Data from the NERSC model MICOM and the IMR model NORWECOM is average values in strategic sections (e.g. into the Barents Sea). The data sets are one-dimensional (time).

3.4 North Atlantic Oscillation index (NAO)

Indices based on the pressure difference between the (normally) high-pressure field over Southern Europe (Lisbon or Gibraltar) and the (normally) low-pressure field over Island. This pressure difference has a major impact on the climate in the Northern regions. The data sets are one-dimensional (time).

3.5 National Centers for Environmental Prediction - NCEP

The NCEP/NCAR Reanalysis Project is a joint project between the National Centers for Environmental Prediction (NCEP, formerly “NMC”) and the National Center for Atmospheric Research (NCAR). The goal of this joint effort is to produce new atmospheric analyses using historical data (1948 onwards) and as well to produce analyses of the current atmospheric state (Climate Data Assimilation System, CDAS). The NCEP-reanalysis data are available in 6hrs resolution in GRIB-format, daily average in NetCDF-format and monthly average in NetCDF.

3.6 Integrated Global Ocean Services System -IGOSS

The IGOSS sea surface temperature (SST) analysis is produced weekly (Sunday to Saturday) on a one-degree grid. The analysis uses mainly satellite SST data which is bias corrected by in situ buoy and ship measurements. This is done by the optimum interpolation (OI) method outlined in Reynolds (1988) and Reynolds and Marsico (1993). The monthly fields are derived by a linear interpolation of the weekly (OI) fields to daily fields, then averaging the daily values over a month. The monthly fields are in the same format and spatial resolution as the weekly fields that are on a 1x1 degree grid size. The data can also be downloaded as weekly or monthly anomalies.

3.7 Comprehensive Ocean-Atmosphere Data Set - COADS

The Comprehensive Ocean-Atmosphere Data Set (COADS) is an extensive collection of surface marine data available for the World Ocean over the past century and a half. Please see the COADS homepage for additional information and electronic documentation about the project, the different releases, and the full suite of observational products and monthly summary statistics. Selected COADS statistics are available in NetCDF format at CD's.

3.8 Arctic Sea Ice cover data – the NORSEX algorithm

The NORSEX data are multi year and total sea ice cover data for the Arctic Oceans, based on analysis of passive microwave satellite data of the SMMR and SMM/I satellites since 1978 to present. Multi-year data with both the NASA team algorithm and the NORSEX algorithm (Svendsen et al, 1983) is provided.

4 Methods

To investigate couplings between (physical) environmental and (biological) fisheries dataset from the FJOMP database some well-known simple statistical methods have been applied, mostly straight correlations and multiple linear regressions, with different time lags (one to four years).

4.1 Correlations

Correlations between the environmental and fisheries time series have been calculated. In the case of surface data (e.g. NCEP, IGOSS) the correlations are calculated between the fisheries time series and the time series at each grid point of surface field of the environmental data set. Time lag of 0-3 years (environmental data 0-3 year before the fishery data) have been evaluated.

An automatically generated data report has been used for the further internal project analysis (Handegard et al., 2000), where correlations higher than ± 0.75 ($c=$) were plotted graphically and correlations higher than ± 0.70 were summarized in tabular form. For 2-D surface covering environmental data, a correlation map was plotted along with the time series of the grid point with the highest correlation with the fisheries time series. Two additional plots are also made:

- 1) Fishery time series and NAO,
- 2) Fishery time series and sea ice index (NCEP ice index around Svalbard, ICES fishery area IIb - see Figure 1).

In the case of monthly environmental data the correlations have been evaluated for each month, except June and November.

In the case of surface fields the correlations are only of relevance if they are in the same geographical region as for the fish data, or in an area, which are within the advective distance for the used time lag between the observational times series. This is the main strength of the correlation maps, where relevant regions are easily identified. At the same time these correlations maps can serve as a tool for researchers in their planning of field investigations as they show where not to search for correlated data sets.

4.2 Multiple regressions

Multiple regression models have been tested on recruitment (number of three year olds) and 0-group index of North East Arctic Cod. Several parameters and time lags (0-5 year) have been evaluated. The variables have been selected on basis of current knowledge and results

from the correlations found. A major issue during this process was to be able to provide prognoses, which means that we were especially looking for variables with annual or multi-annual time lags (1-3 years). The identified best statistical correlations are presented below. However, we want to emphasize that though this “needle in a haystack” method has given good results, the potential of the FJOMP database is much larger in this aspect, and we have only “scratched” the surface of the opportunities in exploring such data sets. The potential for post project activities is accordingly evident.

4.3 Pressure fields and changes in cod age distribution

The time development of the age distribution of North East Arctic cod have been examined by dividing the spawning stock biomass into three age groups, 3-7 year olds, 8 year olds and 9 year and older.

The change in position of the atmospheric sea surface pressure field centre over Iceland has been investigated by dividing the time series into two main periods, 1948-1975 and 1975-1999. Only the winter months have been used in this analysis. The mean and standard deviation for each period has been calculated, as well as the difference in mean and standard deviation between the two periods.

5 Results of selected Case Studies

The complete processed material in FJOMP is too large to be presented in detail in one report and the huge automatically compiled statistical report (Handegard et al, 2000) has been generated and analysed during the FJOMP project implementation (the document has been used internally, but is available on request). Through the many correlations that have been identified (summarized in an internal working document – available on request), there are many of the statistical relations that are unlikely, or at present the connection is not known or explainable, or even very speculative. However, several of the identified statistical connections are very interesting and relevant, because they may have a simple or direct explainable connection chain, which makes them plausible. Furthermore also the relations with identified time lag between the time series of physical and biological data opens for statistical predictability, which opens for use of the various time series in the FJOMP data base to be used for future predictions of fish variables.

The statistical analysis have revealed more than 200 correlations with a value of 0.7 ($c=r$) and higher have been identified, of which 20 are ranked as highly interesting and relevant, in the sense that it seems possible to give a reasonable explanation of the coupling between the fish and climate variable.

In the work with correlations care must be taken. When so many correlations are tested, most certainly some of them will be just coincidental (i.e. high correlation between storks and human babies in Denmark does not necessarily mean that the babies come by storks). It is therefore important that there also is a logical coupling between the variables or a direct explainable relation. If there is a significant level of 0.05 on the correlation this would imply that 5 % of the high correlations cases are coincidental, therefore emphasis has only been put on those cases that might have a logical connection. In some cases the correlation might be high even though the variables seem not to be directly coupled, which may be caused by a common underlying factor (i.e. high correlation between heat flux and juvenile larvae, where the underlying factor might be temperature). These cases are still interesting as the climate variable may serve as an indicator (or proxy) for the common factor which influences the fish variable.

In the following a few cases have been selected and elaborated further. We have limited the cases to yield North East Arctic cod, Norwegian spring spawning herring and Barents Sea capelin, which is three of the most important species in Norwegian fishery. We will in the following use the term “recruitment” widely, from larvae stage up to the age at which the young fish are introduced in the commercial fishery.

5.1 Correlation studies

5.1.1 NAO and recruitment – North east Arctic cod

There is a strong correlation ($c=0.82$) between the 0-group index (log-scale) for North East Arctic cod and NAO winter index two and a half year before (Figure 3). This may have to do with food supply of the cod larvae. We know that there is a connection between zooplankton biomass and NAO one year before (Melle and Holst, 2001), which may be caused by overwintering of zooplankton in the Norwegian Sea. The second year might be explained by the migration of good zooplankton production years towards the Barents Sea, where the 0-group of Cod is situated, thus explaining the response lag of two years between the NAO and 0-group index for North East Arctic cod.

Figure 3: Correlation between 0-group index (log) of North East Arctic cod and NAO winter index (Lisbon-Island) 2.5 year before. The correlation coefficient is 0.82.

5.1.2 SST and recruitment

The IGOSS sea surface temperature in January is correlated with the 0-group log index of North East Arctic cod the same year (Figure 4). The highest positive correlations are found in two areas, the South East part of the Barents Sea and in the central Nordic Seas, with maximum correlation of $c=0.87$ (central Nordic Seas).

It is especially interesting with the high correlation in the South Eastern part of the Barents Sea, which is part of the juvenile breeding area for the cod. The high correlation in the Nordic Seas is not so easy to interpret. The high correlations may be coupled to high transport of warm water to the northern areas, which increase survivability of the larvae, while low

correlations are associated with low transport of warm water (and hence colder conditions and lower survivability and less recruitment).

Figure 4. Correlation map between 0-group index (log) of North East Arctic cod and IGOSS sea surface temperature (SST) in January the same year. Upper left panel shows the correlations, middle left panel the standard deviation of the climate variable, bottom left panel the mean of the climate variable, upper right panel the time series of the fishery time series and the climate variable in the grid cell with the highest correlation, middle right panel the fishery time series and the NAO winter index (Iceland –Lisbon) and the bottom right panel the time series of the fishery variable and the average NCEP ice index in ICES area IIb (around Svalbard, 0 is ice free). In all the three left panels the fishery time series are in blue line and left axis, while the climate variable is in black line and right axis. Note also that the years belong to the fishery time series (and the climate time series have been shifted in case there is a time lag). Note that the best correlation ($c=0.87$) is found in the central Nordic Seas.

5.1.3 NCEP sensible heat flux and Juvenile index of North East Arctic cod

Figure 5 shows the correlation between NCEP sensible heat flux in January and North East Arctic Cod juvenile index same year. The Juvenile index is based on a larvae cruise in June/July (only conducted for the years 1978-1991). The highest correlation ($c=0.96$) is found in a small (1 grid point) area east of Svalbard. This is a region that mostly is covered by ice (sea ice has low sensible heat flux compared to open water), but ice free/low ice concentration years appear occasionally. Though one should be careful to extract definite conclusions from such a single point of very strong correlation and it is tempting to speculate about a reasonable connection. Note that the high correlation is driven by four very strong values, both in larval numbers and in sensible heat flux (which means that there is little ice cover), and is thereby strongly influenced by these high values. The sea ice cover movement passed such a point is mostly influenced by wind and the major ocean currents system, with the currents as a slow varying factor, thereby relatively more important for the inter-annual variation than the short term variability. The cod larvae are hatched in April/May at Lofoten, and can be found around the Tromsø plateau at the time when the juvenile index is surveyed and determined. It is therefore most likely no direct connection between the two variables in

question. Accordingly we have to search for a mechanism that lies behind the variability of both variables. The water temperature is the most likely one, due to the fact that the warm water drives the ice cover north-wards and that the warmer water also influences the larvae growth and food supply positively, thereby increases the survivability. The sensible heat flux in January at this point can therefore act as an indicator of larval survival rate, through the common driving force the water temperature.

The bottom right figure (in Figure 5) shows the correlation ($c=-0.73$) between the juvenile index and the NCEP ice index average over ICES area IIb (around Svalbard), i.e. higher larval survival when there is low ice concentration (and thereby warmer water). This also supports the above arguments.

Figure 5. Correlation map between NCEP sensible heat flux in January and North East Arctic cod juvenile index the same year. See text under Figure 4 for details.

5.1.4 Sea ice cover index and North East Arctic Cod

A high negative correlation ($c=-0.82$) is found between the sea ice index (using the NORSEX algorithm, Svendsen et al. (1983)) and the recruitment, using the numbers of three year olds from VPA of North East Arctic cod two years later.

The sea ice cover index may be seen as a measure of the transport of warmer water into the region (reducing the ice extent). Warm water means better growth conditions when the Cod was younger (1 year old) and better conditions for the zooplankton at that time. Both these factors are favourable for the young cod classes, thereby giving the potential of a stronger year classes of three year olds cod two years later. Another factor that may be important is that low ice concentrations in January usually gives less ice concentration later in the season, and thus a larger area for distribution, and also for production of phytoplankton and zooplankton feeding that year class of cod. The effect might be largest for the one year old classes, thereby giving a two-year time lag.

Figure 6. The correlations between recruits (number of 3 year olds, VPA 1999) of North East Arctic Cod and NORSEX sea ice index in the ICES fishery areas (I east, I west, IIb, Va, XIVa and XIVb see Figure 1) in January 2 years earlier. Note the high correlation ($c=-0.82$) in area I east (Eastern Barents Sea), which is marked with a red circle.

5.2 Multiple regression models

5.2.1 0-group index of North East Arctic cod

A model of the log 0-group index based on North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO) and spawning stock biomass (SSB) 2 year earlier explains ~50 % of the variance during the 0-group index in the period 1966-2001.

The high 0-group correlation with NAO two years earlier ($c=0.80$) might be explained through increased food availability. Melle and Holst (2001) have found that a higher number of larvae of *Calanus Finmarkicus* surviving the winter during the year after a high NAO. This might imply that another year later food supply is still good for cod larvae on their drift northwards along the Norwegian coast. The good recruitment of copepods may also use one year for them to be advected into the Barents Sea, giving a two-years time lag for their impact on the recruitment.

It would be appropriate to use the SSB the same year as the 0-group index. However, there is a high autocorrelation in the spawning stock from one year to another. In order to fully use the time lag of two years in the NAO and 0-group relationship, we evaluated the SSB two years earlier as well. The autocorrelation for SSB (VPA, 2001) during the period 1946-2000 was 0.90 and 0.71 for time lags of one and two years, respectively.

Based on the above results the following model and coefficients can be set up:

$$0\text{-group}_t = 0.19 * NAO_{t-2} + 1.9 * 10^{-6} * SSB_{t-2} + 0.37$$

where 0-group is the log 0-group index for North East Arctic cod, NAO the Lisbon-Island winter atmospheric pressure index and SSB the Spawning stock biomass (in tonnes) from the ICES VPA 2001 without cannibalism. This model has been used to estimate the statistical prognosis for the following two years.

Figure 7. Multiple regression model for 0-group index (log-scale) North East Arctic Cod, with prognoses for 2001-2003. Black line is data, red is model and green is prognosis.

5.2.2 Three year old recruits of North East Arctic cod (1)

A model of the spawning success (i.e. the number of recruits (1 year olds) per unit SSB - spawning stock biomass) based on NAO and SSB 3 year earlier explains ~50 % of the variation for the period 1975-2000.

Based on the above results the following model for the years 1975-2000 can be set up:

$$\text{Rec}_t / \text{SSB}_{t-3} = 230 * \text{NAO}_{t-3} - 0.0029 * \text{SSB}_{t-3} + 2200$$

By multiplying both sides of the equation with SSB the number of recruits can be expressed as:

$$\text{Rec}_t = (230 * \text{NAO}_{t-3} - 0.0029 * \text{SSB}_{t-3} + 2200) * \text{SSB}_{t-3}$$

where Rec is the number of recruits, NAO the Lisbon-Island winter index and SSB is the Spawning stock biomass (tonnes) from the ICES VPA 2001 without cannibalism. This model has been used to estimate the statistical prognosis for the following three years.

For the time period prior to mid 70' this relationship fails. There seems to be two causes for this. First, there is a change in the position of the low-pressure field over Island after mid 70', when it moved into a more eastward position, thus giving narrower isobars along the Norwegian coast for the same value of the NAO index as before mid 70' (i.e. stronger winds). Second, there is a shift in the distribution of the abundance in the age classes towards a higher abundance of younger spawning classes, while the number of older spawners decline. Therefore another model can be used for recruitment prior to 1975.

Based on the above results the following model for the years 1952-1974 can be set up:

$$\text{Rec}_t / \text{SSB}_{t-3} = 290 * \text{skin}_{t-3} - 600 * \text{NAO}_{t-3} - 0.0032 * \text{SSB}_{t-3} + 3600$$

where skin is the NCEP sea surface temperature (degree C) winter average (January-March) in the Barents Sea (71-75°N, 30-45°E). The other variables are the same as for the period 1975-2000 (see above).

Figure 8. Multiple regression models for spawning success for North East Arctic Cod, with prognoses for 2001-2004. The first model yields 1952-1974 and the second 1975-2000. The prognosis is calculated on from the second model.

Figure 9. Recruitment (number of three year olds) of North East Arctic cod. Based on the second model in Figure 8, but multiplied by the SSB.

5.2.3 Three year old recruits of North East Arctic cod (2)

Another statistical model for the number of three years old recruits of North East Arctic cod, developed by Geir Ottersen (pers. com.), have been tested on the data from the FJOMP database. The model uses an autoregressive term for the recruitment and gives $R^2 = 0.50$ and $P\text{-value} < 0.01$ for the period 1969-2000 (individual $P\text{-values}$ are: $\text{rec}_{-1}\text{-rec}_{\text{mean}} = 0.01$, $\text{length}_{0\text{-group}} = 0.15$, $\text{temp}_{\text{Kola}} = 0.12$).

Based on the above results the following model and coefficients can be set up:

$$\log(\text{rec}) = 0.45 * \log(\text{rec}_{t-1} - \text{rec}_{\text{mean}}) + 0.014 * \text{length}_{0,t-3} + 0.38 * \text{temp}_{\text{Kola},t-3} + 17$$

Here rec_{t-1} is the number of recruits the year before, rec_{mean} the average recruitment for the period, $\text{length}_{0\text{-group}}$ the length of the 0-group larvae 3 year earlier and $\text{temp}_{\text{Kola}}$ the yearly average temperature (degrees C) from 0-200 m in the Kola section three years earlier. Note that the 0-group length and the Kola temperature yields the year that the recruits were at the larva stage.

The model gives opportunity for a 3-year prognosis, by using the calculated recruitment (left term in the equation) for one year as the input (first term on the right in the equation) the following year. Care must be taken using this model since errors in the first year prognoses are enhanced in the following years.

Figure 10. Recruitment (number of three year olds) of North East Arctic cod based on the multiple regression model by Geir Ottersen (pers. comm.), with prognoses for the years 2001-2003.

The physical parameter that decides when the “Ottersen-model” can be taken one year further is the annual average Kola section temperature. These aggregated data are normally not available before in February/March the following year. Therefore a variant of the model have been evaluated, where the yearly average Kola section temperature has been exchanged with the average March temperature from 50 to 200 m along the Bjørnøya-Fugløya section. The correlation coefficient between the two series is $c=0.84$ for the period 1980-2000. The Bjørnøya-Fugløya section was not taken before 1977, thus limiting the model to 1980 for recruitment. However, the model has a better fit to the data with $R^2=0.55$ and $P\text{-value} < 0.01$ (individual $P\text{-values}$ are: $\text{rec}_{-1}-\text{rec}_{\text{mean}}=0.60$, $\text{length}_{0\text{-group}}=0.35$, $\text{temp}_{\text{Kola}}=0.12$).

Based on the above results the following model and coefficients can be set up:

$$\log(\text{rec}) = 0.17 * \log(\text{rec}_{t-1}-\text{rec}_{\text{mean}}) + 0.009 * \text{length}_{0,t-3} + 0.52 * \text{tempB-F}_{t-3} + 17$$

This model has been used to estimate the statistical prognosis for the following three years.

Figure 11. Same as Figure 10, but with the temperature from the Bjørnøya-Fugløya section instead of the Kola section. This allows the prognoses to be calculated including 2004.

5.3 Change in cod spawning stock and climate response during the 70'

There seems to be a larger impact of climate variability on cod recruitment after the mid 70'. The NAO winter index gives a significant contribution to regression model (Chapter 5.2.2) after 1975, but for the period 1952-1974 this relationship is not evident. There might be both a biological and a physical explanation to this, which we will discuss.

First, the numbers of older spawners (older than 8 year) have declined rapidly during the last 50 years (Figure 12). Simultaneously the age at which the cod gets mature have also declined, and there is presence of 3-year-old cod that spawn (which didn't occur earlier). With a younger aged spawning stock, the percentage of first time spawners, which have a lower egg quality, increase and these eggs and larvae are therefore more vulnerable to climatic variability.

Second, at the same time there seems to be a shift in the pressure field around Island (Figure 13 - difference in panel and D). The mean pressure field moves eastward, which means that with the same NAO index, the wind field is stronger along the Norwegian coast. Further, the NAO has larger oscillations with a period of about 8 years after the mid 70', which was not present in the previous period.

This may be the reason that we find better couplings between the climate variables and recruitment of cod after the mid 70' than before (as indicated by the horizontal arrow in Figure 12).

Figure 12. The development of the spawning stock biomass (VPA) of North East Arctic cod, divided into three age groups (3-7 year olds, 8 year olds and 9 + year olds).

Figure 2.9: Shift in the low pressure system location. A is map of the mean of SSP for winter months from 1948 to 1975. C: mean of SSP for winter months from 1975 to 1999. B: standard deviation of SSP for winter months from 1948 to 1975. D: standard deviation for winter months from 1975 to 1999. E=C-A and F=D-B. Units are kPa for A and C, Pa for B, D, E and F. Areas in white are areas with no data available in the FJOMP database.

Figure 13. See above. Note how the variation pattern shifts over Island between B and D.

5.4 Norwegian spring spawning herring

For herring a connection was found for the numbers of recruits (0 year olds in 10^9) using 0-group log index the same year, spawning stock biomass (in 10^6 tonnes) one year earlier and NCEP skin (sea surface) temperature (in degree C) in the Norwegian Sea ($64-70^\circ\text{N}$, $6^\circ\text{W}-8^\circ\text{E}$) the same year.

Model with coefficients:

$$\text{Rec}_t = 68 * \text{skin}_{t-3} + 240 * \text{0-group}_t + 6.4 * \text{SSB}_{t-1} - 19000$$

The model does not give access for prognoses (prognoses can be made after the 0group data are available), since two of the variables are from the same year as the recruits.

The model gave $R^2=0.80$ for the investigated period, and $P<0.01$ (individual P-values are: skin: 0.10, 0-group:<0.01, SSB: 0.21).

Figure 14. Multiple regression model for Recruitment (0 year olds) of Norwegian spring spawning herring. Black line is data and blue is model. Note that this regression model does not give possibility for prognoses.

5.5 Barents Sea capelin

The model has been tested on the years 1982-2001 (1981-2000 for the dependent variables).

Model with coefficients:

$$\text{Rec}_t = -35 * \text{Temp}_{t-1} + 0.45 * \text{0-group}_{t-1} + 0.1 * \text{matbio}_{t-1} - 55$$

where Rec is the numbers of recruits in 10^9 , Temp the skin temperature (SKT_{sf}) in degree Celsius from the NCEP reanalysed database average from January to March and over the area between $30-45^\circ\text{E}$ and 71° to 75°N one year earlier, 0-group is the capelin 0-group log index one year earlier (survey estimates back-calculated to 1st August) and matbio the capelin maturing biomass (length greater than 14 cm in 10^3 Tonnes) one year earlier.

The Model have $R^2=0.73$ and P-value < 0.01 , with all individual P-values < 0.06 . The one year time lag of the dependent variables gives opportunity to provide a prognoses for the following year.

Figure 15. The figure shows the number of recruits (one year olds) of Barents Sea Capelin (black) and the model fit (red), together with the one year prognoses for 2002 (green).

6 Prognoses

Prognoses for recruitment to the fish stocks are of vital importance for fishery management. Also the commercial fishing fleet needs this information in decisions concerning future investment and fishing strategies. During the work with FJOMP project we have managed to use historical observations to derive predictive models, with prognostic possibilities for one to three years ahead for a few of the key commercial species in Norwegian waters.

The future recruitment estimated by the regression models (as presented above) is given in Table 1. For North East Arctic cod several models are used. The difference in estimated values are due to two causes. First, the models are simplifications of the complex nature of recruitment and do not explain all of the variation. Second, there is uncertainty in input data.

An estimation of these uncertainties has not been evaluated. This should be a major point in future investigations.

In order to be of any practical use these models need to be updated on an operational basis. The third column of Table 1 indicates which month the data is available for advancing the prognoses another year.

0-group index of North East Arctic cod

The prognosis shows a decrease in cod larva in 2003. Given a high correlation between the 0-group log index and the number of three year old the next year of $c=0.90$ (for the period 1978-1997) this implies a decrease in the number of three year olds in 2004.

Recruits (number of 3 year olds) of North East Arctic cod

In general the prognoses from the models show medium recruitment in 2001-2003, followed by a decrease 2004, thou there are differences both in the prognostic values and in the trend.

Recruits (1 year olds) of Barents Sea capelin

The prognosis shows a medium level for 2002, about the same as in 2001.

Table 1. The table gives an overview of the different models, with prognoses estimates of the variable in question. The given month indicate when the prognoses can be extended for another year. N/A indicates that prognosis from the multiple regression model is not valid for this year. The t in the column "Prognosis available" indicates the year when the prognosis can be made, t is the first year in the prognosis.

Species	Variable	Prognoses period (yr)	Prognoses available	2002 Prognoses	2003 Prognoses	2004 Prognoses
North East Arctic cod	0-group, log (0 year olds)	2	October (t-1)	1.3	0.6	N/A
North East Arctic cod	Recruits (3 year olds) (NAO model)	4	May (t-1)	$4.8 \cdot 10^8$	$5.0 \cdot 10^8$	$2.8 \cdot 10^8$
North East Arctic cod	Recruits (3 year olds) (Kola section model)	3	January/ February (t)	$6.5 \cdot 10^8$	$6.7 \cdot 10^8$	$6.1 \cdot 10^8$
North East Arctic cod	Recruits (3 year olds) (B-F section model)	3	October (t-1)	$6.7 \cdot 10^8$	$6.0 \cdot 10^8$	$4.8 \cdot 10^8$
Barents Sea capelin	Recruits (1 year olds)	1	October (t-1)	$206 \cdot 10^9$	N/A	N/A

7 Summary and Conclusions

In this study we have acquired a large database (FJOMP) of more than 70 marine environmental and fishery stock related datasets. The activities have been pioneering in the acquisition and joint analysis of such a large quality of environmental and fisheries data. The increasing length of the available time series of data that entirely are based on satellite Earth observations or modelling results, which include parameters from EO data sources, are growing. The length of many EO data records are also exceeding 30 years of duration, which makes them relevant to detect climatic long term changes that are of relevance for both research and management. This FJOMP study has addressed some of these relations of relevance to the fisheries research and management.

The effect of climate variation on fish recruitment and stock status has been investigated. Climate and fishery variables in the FJOMP database has been systematically correlated, also with various time lags (1 to 3 years), in order to search for relevant relationships between physical and biological variables. Without any prejudices and using up to three years of time lag between the time series we have searched through these data to identify correlations that are significant. In this process more than 200 sets of correlations with a correlation coefficient better than ± 0.7 were identified. Through an individual inspection of these relations most of them were discarded (due to unrealism or not “explainable” at present) and a remaining 20 cases were evaluated as highly interesting, with an explainable cause for the identified variations. Multiple regression models have been used to further improve some of the most promising and explainable correlations identified. The following most interesting relationships between climate variables and fish recruitment are identified:

- A correlation of 0.82 for a time lag of two years between the North East Arctic cod 0-group index and the NAO winter index for the period 1978-1997.
- A correlation of 0.87 for zero time lag between the North East Arctic cod 0-group index and the IGOSS sea surface temperature in the Nordic Seas in January for the period 1982-1997. High correlations were also found in the south eastern parts of the Barents Sea.
- A correlation of 0.96 with zero time lag between the North East Arctic cod juvenile index and the NCEP sensible heat flux in a point east of Svalbard (at the ice edge) in January for the period 1978-1991.
- A correlation of -0.81 for a time lag of two year between the number of recruits (three year olds) of North East Arctic cod and the sea ice index in the eastern part of the Barents Sea (ICES area I east) in January for the period 1981-1998.
- A regression model describing 49% of the variance for the 0-group index of North East Arctic cod based on the NAO winter index and the spawning stock biomass two year earlier for the period 1966-2002.
- A regression model describing 46% of the variance for the number of recruits (three year olds, VPA) of North East Arctic cod based on the NAO winter index and the spawning stock biomass three year earlier for the period 1975-2002.
- A regression model describing 57% of the variance for the number of recruits (three year olds, VPA) of North East Arctic cod based on the recruitment (three year olds) the year before, the length of the 0-group larvae and the yearly average temperature in the Kola section three year earlier for the period 1966-2001.
- A regression model describing 60% of the variance for the number of recruits (three year olds, VPA) of North East Arctic cod based on the recruitment (three year olds)

the year before, the length of the 0-group larvae and the average temperature in March in the Bear Island - Bird Island section three year earlier for the period 1980-2002.

- A regression model describing 85% of the variance for the number of recruits (three year olds) of Norwegian spring spawning herring based on the average NCEP skin temperature in the Norwegian Sea and the 0-group index three year earlier and the NAO winter index five years earlier for the period 1973-2002.
- A regression model describing 72% of the variance for the number of recruits (one year olds) of Barents Sea capelin based on the average NCEP skin temperature in the Barents Sea, the 0-group index and the mature biomass one year earlier for the period 1982-2002.

The NAO index and sea surface temperature data are the two climate controlled factors that seems to be the most important for the fish recruitment, although sensible heat flux, sea ice cover and heat transport (into the Barents Sea) also are found to give good and plausible relations towards the fish recruitments. Especially the NAO index gives good relations to several recruitment parameters for North East Arctic cod, while the sea surface temperature is more important for Barents Sea capelin and Norwegian spring spawning herring.

The analysis presented is just a start on "scratching" on the information included in this coupled physical and fishery marine database. To fully exploit the values of this database it needs to be maintained with new data records and the methods of analysis and evaluation should be refined in order to become more robust.

Since this work indicates clear effects on recruitment from climate, it is a great challenge to investigate these effects together with multi-species population dynamics, especially including cod, herring and capelin simultaneously.

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